

Explanatory of Relationship between Learning Motivation and Learning Performance

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Abstract—In this paper, the relationship between learning motivation and learning performance is explored by using exchange theory. The relationship is concluded that external performance can raise learning motivation and then increase learning performance. The internal performance should be not completely neglected and the external performance should be not attached important excessively. The parents need self-study and must be also reeducated. The existing education must be improved in raise of internal performance. The incorrect learning thinking will mislead the students, parents, and educators of next generation, when the students obtain good learning performance in the learning environment with excess stimulants. Over operation of external performance will result abnormal learning thinking and violating learning goal. Learning is not only to obtain performance. Learning quality and learning performance will be limited as without learning motivation. The best learning motivation is, the best learning performance is. The learning for reward is not good for learning performance. Strategies of promoting life-long learning are including the encouraging for learner, establishment of good interaction learning environment, and the advertisement of the merit and the importance of life-long learning, which can let the learner with the correct learning motivation.

Keywords—exchange theory, learning motivation, learning performance, learning quality

I. INTRODUCTION: ORIGIN OF EXCHANGE THEORY

IN 1958, the society exchanged theory is proposed [1]. The application of exchange theory in education has been researched. The exchange theory is, afterwards, extended to the establishment of utmost scale exchange theory in 1964 [2], and is synthesized with the mark interacted principle in 1972 [3]. The foundation of exchange theory is based on the discussion of human's subject by using the sociology theory, and the exchange theory is concentrated to the model of psychology, the crowd, and the social life fundamental mode in sociological theory. The learning motivation and learning performance are currently discussed by using the exchange theory in this report.

II. THE EXCHANGE BEHAVIOR

The special properties of “exchange” behavior are stated in this section. The exchange is a kind of sociological behavior, which the “exchange” is an activity between two persons at least, and is with the values of reward or expanding. The pigeon theory is defined in the exchange relations of unidirectional participation, but the human's exchange is bidirectional, moreover, the all needs two animals at least.

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The activity of bidirectional exchange is by use of strengthens which is enhanced and influenced each other. The exchange theory is including five propositions, as shown in Fig. 1, which contains successful proposition, stimulation proposition, value proposition, deprive and elimination of satisfy propositions, and attack and commending propositions.

Fig. 1 Five propositions of exchange theory.[1]

The successful proposition is a kind of unique behavior in sociology. The unique behavior is that when someone obtains the reward by special action in usual, they will be glad to being engaged in the special action. For the statement of stimulation proposition, if the present stimulation is similarly with the past stimulation, somebody could take the action. For the value proposition, if the more valuable things to him are, the more the things will be possibility engaged in. For description of deprive and elimination of satisfy propositions, if somebody is often obtained some special rewards, the rewards will not be value for him gradually. Attack and commending proposition is defined that when the anticipated reward is not attained after action, the attack motion will be possibility displayed [4]. The relationship between learning motivation and learning performance is discussed by using the exchange theory only including use of successful proposition, stimulation proposition, and value proposition in this report.

III. RESEARCH RESULT: EXPLANATORY NOTES OF EDUCATION PERFORMANCE USING EXCHANGE THEORY

Annotation of exchange theory in education performance is discussed in this section. Education quality although cannot be wholly defined by the education performance and education goals, the standardization of education performances and the education goals should be aimed in the learning motivation. The definitions of education performance should not be only localized in the study score or the race achievement and in the thinking of benefits exchange by themselves. The education performances generally contained the internal performance and external performance. The external performances are the result of knowledge study which is exposed by using examination in general, and the representation of personal behavior which is disclosed by observation of other people.

The two kinds of external performances are belonged to the utilitarianism of exchange theory. The internal performance is one kind of performance of long-term influence in personality. Therefore, the two performances should be integrated as the figures of education quality, which should not pay attention to the external performance merely. If the external performance or greatest reward is considered in partial, the education quality will not be achieved well. In this paper, the education performance is discussed on focus of relationship between learning motivation and learning performance in the education quality.

IV. RESEARCH RESULT: DISCUSSIONS OF LEARNING MOTIVATION AND LEARNING PERFORMANCE

Firstly, education quality is explored by using successful proposition. For some special action, when student often obtains the reward after the actions, then student will be glad to engage the actions [4]. The learning for student is frequently under the passive situation in study. The learning motivation of student in the school, possibility, is influenced by their parents. Most of students obtained external performances owing to their parents' dignified taught in without volunteer. The learning of without volunteer is perhaps able to produce the well learning performance in short-term, but still it will affect the long-term apparent performance in external learning performance. This learning of without volunteer exist a risk for good learning quality, because of incorrect learning motivation. Although the learning motivation of school-age child is not easily established actually, but the volunteer learning motivation such as technology learning is extremely not existed in current school education even in technology university education currently. Even though the volunteer learning motivation of technology is existed, the reason of volunteer learning is perhaps in order to examine or entering a higher school, which is the majority account for all. These abnormal learning motivations are the key sources of abnormal learning performance, which results in good obvious external performance in short term and then produces bad unobvious internal performances in long term. Because of the unobservation in short term and unnecessary in society requirement for internal performance, the most of parents will pay attention to external performances but not internal performances, even if they understand the internal performance which is very important also for your child. The most of students do not understand the important of internal performances, but many students understand the important of external performances. The parents, teachers, and educators, therefore, must be reeducated to enhance the thinking of internal performance. The parents' vanity and wish (or dream) is also the enhancements of learning activity for student, but it is not real learning motivation. The parents' incorrect thinking also influenced their child and student indirectly, which is not intrinsic education, but visionary. The student is also continuously influenced by the visionary and then it will be transmitted from generation to generation. What are the selections of expertise and school for the entrance of higher grade school? The solution may be vocation situation, personal interest, or parents' demands. Learning quality and learning performance is absolutely depended on learning motivation in

long term, even though student has obtained the well external performances. As student is without well internal performances, the job enthusiasm, vocation ethics, and vocation development will be insufficiency in future in their work. The good academic record can increase learning motivation, and then enhance the learning performance, but if the internal performance is completely neglected or the external performance is over enhanced, the well character of person will be unable to be produced. The revolution of learning motivation for student in school must be simultaneously accomplished by teachers, educators, and government according to successful proposition theory. For the stimulation proposition, if the past stimulation is similar with current stimulation, then somebody will make a action in more. Afterward, assigned class in ability of many junior high schools is implemented recently, which is a use of exchange theory of stimulation proposition. As the assigning classes are established, the proportion of students entering schools a higher grade is raised. The higher proportion is likely false. The student which entering the school is to obtain well external performance in examination, but not really study knowledge, which results in commercialization of learning quality after "star school" is formed. Perhaps, many schools have been regard as business. Perhaps, students have been regard as merchandise in school. High entering proportion in higher school has been also regard as the figure of school quality. Internal performance has been regard as figure of school quality in fewer and fewer schools, because of without reward and without importance for learning performance, which is created by the apparent environment. Therefore, because of stimulation of the apparent reward, the stimulations are utilized even more in school management. The assigned class in ability is only a product or tool under the stimulants and rewards. More stimulants are produced under the unceasing vicious circle. These stimulants can increase more benefits, which causes that much more assigned class are established in school. The education performance is consequently obtained under such exchange theory. Such education policy is conformed to the teaching of examination leadership, which is completely the education way and idea of external performance figure. Students should not accept the learning of stimulation environment since childhood, which creates the extremely negative education idea in them and deeply embeds in their innermost feelings. When students got with negative education idea and then eventually obtained excellent learning performance under the stimulation environment, the next generation students, the parents, and the school administration, and even education policy formulation institution will be misled by the abnormal education thinking. A colossus educating machine is formed abnormally, and even violates education goal, which is the result of over operation of apparent stimulation.

The third exchange theory is the value theory. The more is it value to him, the more is it engaged to motion [4]. Although every thing has a certain value for people in education, all regarding educational strategic should be executed on the line. It is worth that student's cognition of apparent value must be explored in detail, because the student may does not really understand the true learning value.

Two things are unknown for students. Firstly, the students do not really understand what are the learning internal performance and learning external performance, so as to think no performance for learning, and then give up learning. In this situation, the tutor and civilization are very important in help. If no tutor and civilization, the learning motivation of student will be lost. Therefore, the multi-dimensional pipeline for learning and the multi-dimensional study are correct and important, and increase of learning opportunity is also right for student. The establishment of correct concept of learning values is important and must instruct the student, otherwise, the student will be lead into wrong thinking in learning. The second, it is important let student understand the learning values. Then, the student will hardly make great efforts in learning. It will be harmful for vocation in future, if the students don't understand the learning values. If the students think that the learning is only to obtain rewards in future, but not obtain internal value for person, so called utilitarianism, even though the learning performance is high, when the external performance is declined or disappeared, the students will be no longer continuous learning, because the student's recognition is that the learning is no values. If the learning performance is merely the acquisition of value, or the learning motivation is produced by apparent value merely, then the teaching is actually defeated. The teaching and learning are not only individual behavior, but also they are a relative behavior for person to person, because the teaching and learning are all in an environment of social structure. The life-long study is a very good example for explanatory of relationship between learning motivation and learning performance. Most life-long learning is initiative, but it is also coordinated to study in organization. Learning quality and performance is limited, if the life-long study is passive, which not only waste the spirit, the money, and the time, but also result in wrong learning thinking.

How to establish the good life-long learning model? How to enhance the learning motivation? All of encourage for learner, establishment of good interaction learning environment, and advertisement of the real merit and importance of life-long learning are the key factors for the enhancement of learning motivation and learning performance.

V. PROPOSITION OF LEARNING MOTIVATION AND LEARNING PERFORMANCE

On the whole, explanatory of learning motivation and learning performance can be introduced as above statement by using exchange theory. The propositions are proposed as below and as shown in Fig. 2.

The successful learning affects learning performance.

- Student's learning is influenced by parents and learning system.
- Short-term external performance influenced long-term external performance.
- Short-term external performance could have risk for learning quality.
- School-age child's learning motivation must be established.

- Learning motivation of after assigned class influenced learning quality.
- Internal performance is related with learning motivation.
- The parent's pressure to child influenced the learning performance.
- External environment including parents, overall learning structure and teaching thinking influenced learning performance.
- Different learning motivation has different learning quality and learning performance.

Learning performance will be raised by using the stimulations.

- Assigned class in ability in school will be unable to raise all learning performance.
- The learning reward may increase internal performance.
- Short term external performance and reward can stimulate learning motivation which is the vicious circle.
- Student's learning performance will be influenced by the stimulation and external environment.

Correct concept of learning value can increase learning performance.

- If learning performance is not really understood, the learning will not possess performance and then the student will give learning up at initial stage.
- School entrance of multi-dimensional pipeline and multi-dimensional learning are correct, which can increase the learning opportunity for student.
- The wrong performance cognition will result in unfavorable job in future.

Fig. 2 Explanatory of learning motivation and learning performance (Source: this study)

VI. CONCLUSIONS

- The examination score can raise learning motivation and then increase learning performance. But if the internal performance is completely neglected or the external performance is excessively attached important, the student will be not teaching with personality moral character.
- Except parents and teacher, education environment and policy also play an important role for change of the stimulant

in learning motivation. The parents need self-learning. The parents also must accept reeducation. Recognition of teacher and educator of school must be consistent with each other. Also, the establishment of education policy and execution of executive institution also must be consistent with standard. Time is the important key factor for revolution of learning motivation. The existing education must be improved in raise of internal performance. Because the apparent enhancements were very difficult to be removed, education recognition of all educators must be consistent.

- The students may obtain good learning performance in the learning environment with excess stimulants, which the incorrect thinking will be delivered to the students, parents, and educators of next generation.
- Abnormal learning thinking and violating education goal are because of over operating of external performance.
- If learning is only to obtain value, or the learning motivation is produced due to the value, then the learning motivation is actually failed.
- Education is the relationship between person and person, because it is an overall social structure.
- Life-long learning is a very good example for explanatory of learning motivation and learning performance. If the life-long learning is to suit the job in business, but not initiative, then the learning quality and learning performance are limited.
- The learning motivation of life-long learning and job training are very important. The best learning motivation is, the best learning performance is.
- The learning for reward is not good for learning performance. Strategies of promoting life-long learning are including the encouraging for learner, establishment of good interaction learning environment, and the advertisement of the merit and the importance of life-long learning, which can let the learner with the correct learning motivation.

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